
AN OVERVIEW OF ELECTRONIC SERVICES IN ACADEMIC LIBRARY

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Abstract:

An academic library is a place where educational reading materials are available. Academic libraries are located in educational institutions such as schools, colleges, and universities. Library services are recognized as the primary responsibility of libraries. The aim of an academic library is to act as a support system and assist stakeholders such as teachers and students in the teaching, learning, and research activities conducted in their parent institution by providing various library services. Libraries have been providing their services for a long time but gradually these services have become available in electronic form now the services are being created so that the users can enjoy these services in their daily life. The present study attempts to provide an overview of various electronic services in academic libraries.

Keywords: *Academic library services, School library, College library, University knowledge resource center, Electronic Services*

Introduction:

There are four types of libraries namely academic libraries, public libraries, special libraries, and national libraries. Different types of libraries provide different services according to their information needs. Promotion of various information products and services is a prime objective of today's libraries and dissemination of pinpoint information is the need for hours. Academic libraries in the present study include three types namely school libraries, college libraries, and university libraries. It is the responsibility of the library to provide library services to every student enrolled in the educational institution. A library is

not only an information center but also an information service center.

A librarian is a person who manages information systems in multiple formats. Information sources are disseminated through specially designed services based on user demand. The main objective of every library is to provide library services to meet the reading needs of the users. A library preserves three types of sources of information namely primary, secondary and tertiary. The library provides information to the user as per the demand of the user and is expected to provide appropriate information as per the need of the user.

Need For Study:

In today's scenario, libraries and their services are an important part of the development process. Users must provide services as requested. Academic library services guide the readers and help them in any academic study task. Regarding the need for library service awareness, "Satish Kumar in his article states that the needs of the users are diverse. They are as follows.

- 1) To create demand and interest among readers to use library resources and services.
- 2) To help identify quality products and services.
- 3) To provide a process and develop a theoretical framework.
- 4) Determining the future of library products and services.
- 5) To interact with the users of the library(Kumar, 2020).

Gaur says in his book about reference service

- 1) Need to obtain information quickly for specific requirement area;
- 2) Awareness of newly generated information is difficult;
- 3) Need for selection of information, as there is an overabundance of information;
- 4) Would specialization only in a restricted subject area;
- 5) Obtain copies of the required material or the material itself and
- 6) Criteria for evaluation and selection of reference material(Gaur, 2013).

The Objective of the Study:

- 1) To identify the academic library services.
- 2) To have an awareness of academic library services.

Concept of Academic Library Services:

Libraries provide information resources for specific and defined communities. Public libraries serve all types of users. Specific libraries provide information related to a specific subject. However, academic libraries serve students, teachers, research scholars, and all members associated with educational institutions. Every library performs three basic functions which are selecting, collecting, and providing services to users. According to Patel, in his thesis, some librarians have suggested four basic functions in the field of library service.

- 1) Informing users about library management.
- 2) Helping the user to resolve his/her queries.
- 3) Helping users to choose good works.
- 4) To promote libraries in society

These functions serve to provide reference and information services even in digital environments(Patel, 2015).

Definition of Academic Library:

Wikipedia (2021) defines academic libraries in higher education as, "An academic library is a library that is attached to a higher education institution and serves two complementary purposes: to support the curriculum, to support the research of the university faculty and students."

Literature Review:

Cabonero, Chastene, Bannog, Zella, Dacanay, Mia, and Camonayan (2019) in their study discussed the electronic selective dissemination of information through messaging and mail in academic libraries. A survey was conducted at St. Mary's University of Bayombong in the Philippines. The study

found that most users preferred text messages to get information from the University Learning Resource Center and the study showed awareness of e-SDI services and the need for fast internet connectivity.

Akwang (2020) in his study on conceptual description of marketing strategies for ICT-based Services in Academic libraries and analysed overview of marketing strategies and ICT-based services. The paper shows that libraries face several challenges in marketing ICT-based services in academic libraries, and the study suggests that libraries should subscribe to several curriculum-based databases to attract users.

Moruwawon (2020) reviewed the benefits of e-resources and applications in the use of academic library services in his study based on a literature review. He described the challenges and strategies for enhancing effective academic library services. Inadequate e-resources, limited computer facilities, inadequate funds, etc. The study noted that many challenges are faced in providing e-resources.

Oyelude, Ola, and Adeniran (2021) designed an information architecture model for an academic library system framework in their study of service improvement in a hybrid academic library system. The library system and framework of library operations have been analysed and also the operation trends in the library sections like cataloguing, bindery volume section, reference section, issue-return loan rate etc.

Murphy, Lewis, McKillop, and Stoeckle (2022) studied the academic and archive emerged services of during the COVID-19 period in University of Calgary. There are described various services useful for digital environment and how to deliver these services of the

university users. The study highlights on online work teams, online library chat service, remote services for special collections and archives, virtual 360-degree tours, and digital collections agreements.

Types of Academic Libraries:

After India's independence, the Secondary Education Commission's Report on Education of 1952-1953 drew attention to the place of libraries in schools. A.I. Mudaliar presided.

In the field of education, higher education includes the university. In the 1948-1949 reports of the University Education Commission on Libraries, the commission discussed in detail the need for libraries to be central to the educational system of the university.

The role of the library in higher education was discussed in the Education and National Development Report of the Education Commission held in 1964-1966, when the Chairman of the Commission, Dr. D. S. Kothari was.

UGC Library Committee Chairman Dr. S.R. Ranganathan was. In 1959, the University Grands Commission published a report entitled "University and College Libraries", which included the proceedings of the symposium "From Publishers to Readers" held in March 1957 and the report of the Library Committee. The report produced a comprehensive collection of library recommendations covering all aspects of college and university library institutions and services (Yadav, 2018).

1) School Libraries:

A school library is a type of academic library that has limited academic reading material and includes school students, teachers, and sometimes parents as readers. A school library helps students

develop a love of reading and supports the academic curriculum. (Wikipedia, 2022).

2) College Libraries:

A college library is another type of academic library that has student-centered and course-oriented academic reading materials and includes college students, professors, and members associated with the college as readers.

3) University Knowledge Resource Center

University Knowledge Resource Center is the Heart of the University has more reading material than school and college libraries. Libraries handling research-oriented and academic reading material include graduate students, postgraduate students, research students, professors and other university staff as readers.

Electronic Services in Academic Library:

These services are useful in libraries for the current scenario. Akwang (2020) described some of the electronic library services in their study.

1) Internet Service:

The Internet is a tool through which many online services can be enjoyed. The Internet enables electronic-based library services to be provided to users faster and in less time. A library can collect many online information tools and provide them to the readers through various services. The Internet plays an important role in academic libraries as it helps to keep course-based reading materials like e-books, e-reports, e-journals, video films, sound recordings, pictures, etc. in electronic form and online.

2) Bulletin Board Service:

Services like bulletin boards in academic libraries help users to get news about many current affairs. This service is

known as a public newsgroup or discussion forum and can be used to post messages about many of the library's services. The service can be used by the library to send various educational reading materials such as messages, articles, announcements, notices and latest news about the library. All users can view, post, retrieve and read new messages simultaneously through the Internet.

3) Electronic Selective Dissemination Of Information (E-Sdi):

Dissemination of selected information in academic libraries is a service provided primarily in college and university libraries. A service such as Electronic SDI can create profiles of library users and send them information or reading materials by mail, as well as form groups of research students and provide research-related reading materials. E-SDI is used for accurate information needs of users in academic libraries and this service also appears to be a personalized service.

4) Current Awareness Service:

This service includes new information, new books, new journals, magazines and newspapers arriving in the academic library. This service works to update the knowledge of users in the field of education. CAS provides a bulletin containing bibliographic entries, new tables of contents, selected newspaper articles, current selected information, and book chapters disseminated to users as needed. A lot of information can now be made available electronically on a college or university website, including sites such as e-journals, e-newsletters, electronic databases, etc. Electronic library services are a means through which such services can reach maximum number of users.

5) Web-Based Online Public Access Catalogue (Web-Opac):

This service is also known as "WebCats". This service helps the user to access the electronic resources provided by the library online. Through this service, cataloguing of electronic resource materials from all participating libraries around the world can be viewed. Web links are also provided by Web-OPEC to assist users in locating resources containing relevant records and publication information. Now there is also a new web OPAC application that provides access to more than 1000 libraries. Web OPEC offers several library facilities such as the use of Boolean operators to locate reading material, renewal of materials on loan, reservations for materials, and library instructions that also allow for help using command boxes.

6) Electronic Document Delivery Services:

It is a service through which a user can request the library for the documents they need and is also called a value-added service. This service is used in academic libraries to provide book chapters, journal articles and other reading materials to users on demand. It can be provided in electronic format such as Portable Document Format (PDF), image, as well as Word format. This service requires users to provide their mail id. And the desired documents can be delivered to the library by mail. Another option is to send multiple links and website URLs via mail.

7) Digital Library Service:

An academic library has many types of reading materials and the use of reading materials is essential. Printed historical reading material, old reference books, past question papers, indexes, bibliographies, abstracts etc. These reading materials used by academic users can be

brought into electronic form using new technological methods. Many printed reading materials can be scanned into computer scanners and converted into electronic resources, and digital formats of these electronic resources can be made available to online and offline readers. This service can also be provided through the library website. This service will make library information resources global, reduce library space and save readers' time.

8) Online User Education Service:

User education plays an important role in academic libraries as a means of introducing library resources and services to students. Provides formal and informal education through user education service to introduce the library and maximize its resource utilization, as well as guide existing library users. Online user education in the form of educational programs such as online information literacy, research consultation, online library orientation, library skills, database introduction or instruction will save librarians and users time, help users of information services and tools, and have a positive effect on self-learning.

9) Institutional Repository Service (IRS):

The Institutional Repository Service (IRS) makes these publications available to readers because many publications are published within an academic institution. Through this service printed publications of the organization can be scanned and kept in electronic form. These sources include journal articles, dissertations, conference papers, newspaper clippings, etc. Many research projects are ongoing at colleges or universities and places of higher education, and their institutional repositories may be included in the service

through this service. The Institutional Repository Service of an academic institution shall collect, store and digitize publications, articles, and other materials of the institution and make them available to readers through the Internet on the institution's website for research purposes.

10) Audio-Visual Service:

Audio-visual services provide readers with sound recordings, films, educational presentations, projective equipment, computer software, interactive whiteboards, slides, slide-tape presentations, live theatre productions, etc. This includes now online learning platforms have been created through new higher education and users can also study from home through this technological device. Through this service, readers get information of interesting value. The benefit of this service is maximized for disabled as well as blind users.

11) Ask A Librarian Service:

This is known as virtual reference service and is a free service that helps readers online. Allows readers to receive advice, suggestions, text messages about the library via e-mails, links, widgets on the library website, and live chat software to answer questions.(Akwang, 2020)

Service Delivery Methods:

Academic library services are provided through printed books and electronically. It is the responsibility of the academic library to make the following services available to the readers in the form they want.

Library reading facilities, book exchange, readers' advisory services, community information services and library services using electronic media, etc.

Service Delivery Methods in School Libraries:

A school library is responsible for ordering, cataloguing, maintaining and exchanging books to meet the reading needs of students and teachers.

- To create interest and curiosity among teachers and students about books and reading materials in the library, and to hold exhibitions recognizing their interest.
- To impart knowledge of reading skills to the students to learn and inculcate the value of books in the mind of the readers so as to promote personal development.
- To develop a life-long capacity for students to focus on self-learning.
- To enable teachers and other teaching staff to use library resources for academic development and participation in various school programs.
- To develop a sense of confidence in accessing information in the school library.

Service Delivery Methods in College Libraries:

A college library is larger than a school library and has a large collection of books, providing young students with a wide range of subjects and in-depth information.

- To prepare undergraduate students for in-depth study in various disciplines using modern technology.
- To prepare college students to take up higher responsibilities in organizations such as civic organizations, schools, professional establishments, businesses, industries, and government departments.

- To provide textbooks and adequate physical facilities for study by the library.
- To train students in law, engineering, technology and medicine and to provide specialized materials and bibliography for research students and faculty.
- To provide training in the use of electronic services of the library.

Service Delivery Methods In University Knowledge Resource Center:

The aims and functions of the university include creating social awareness by providing managerial and intellectual leadership to various fields such as health, engineering, government, agriculture, industry, defence, education and law.

Conducting awareness programs for maximum use of electronic resources in university libraries. To promote research and work towards making reading material available to all research groups. Promoting ideals of social justice, national integration and religious tolerance with a view to interfaith equality (Yadav, 2018).

Conclusion:

As a service organization the main objective of the library is to meet the information needs of the users. An attempt has been made to analyse various services aimed at attracting readers' attention in academic library services. These services are now developing in electronic as well as digitization mode. Online mode is the need of today's environment as user can access information at any moment and also saves time of every user. This article is useful for academic library users.

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